

Model Parenting Education And Stimulation Play Therapy In Growth And Early Childhood Development

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Abstract

Background Of The Study : Children experience growth and development from birth to adulthood. During the toddler stage, the growth and development of children occurs very quickly. Knowledge about growth, development and stimulation of play therapy is very important for a mother to have. This will have an effect on stimulating play therapy to increase growth and development in early childhood. Parental participation in early childhood education is pivotal for child growth and development, one of which is through play therapy and stimulation. However, most parents are unaware of the importance of their participation and are lack skills to implement good practice. Thus identification of models for parenting education and stimulation of play therapy in early childhood. Family environment is also said to be the most important environment, because most of the children's life is in the family, so that the most education received by early childhood is in the family. Parenting education for parents who have early childhood in PAUD (Early Childhood Education) with day care is manifested in a way of assisting parents in stimulating play therapy and how to educate children.

Aim Of The Study : To develop and validate the module models of parenting education and stimulation of play therapy in early childhood growth and development. **Methodology :** The methodological study conducted to examine the content validity of the models of parenting education and stimulation of play therapy in early childhood growth and development book through a two-step process (development and judgment). At the first step, domain determination, sampling (item generation) and instrument formation and at the second step, content validity ratio was performed. Suggestions of expert panel and item impact scores are used to examine the instrument face validity.

Results: The making of the book "Model Parenting Education (Stimulation of Playing Therapy for Early Childhood Growth and Development)" has been reviewed by 2 expert examiners and tested on 22 PAUD teachers from 11 PAUD and 11 parents of PAUD children from 11 PAUD in Yogyakarta.

Conclusion : Models of parenting education and stimulation of play therapy in early childhood development and development can be applied to PAUD in PAUD.

Keywords: Parenting Education, Stimulation Of Play Therapy, Growth, Early Childhood Development.

INTRODUCTION

The growth and development of children occurs very quickly. A period like this is basic and will not be repeated in the next life. The attention given to childhood will greatly determine the quality of human life in the future. Humans develop from one developmental period to another, they

experience different behavioral changes caused by the problems or tasks that are required and appear at each development period is different. One of the developmental tasks is to form independence, discipline, and emotional sensitivity in children. One way to achieve this developmental task can be done through stimulation of play therapy from an early age¹.

Knowledge about growth, development and stimulation of play therapy is very important for a mother to have. This will have an effect on stimulating play therapy to increase growth and development in early childhood. Mothers who have a good level of knowledge have a good understanding of growth, development and stimulation of play therapy. The knowledge of parents, especially mothers, plays a very important role in early childhood behavior and forms optimal growth and development, because children's attention and observation cannot be separated from the attitudes and behavior of parents². Mothers can act as coaches for children in stimulating play therapy, giving the right example to children, providing motivation and praise to children, giving rewards when the child's behavior is good and not yelling when an accident occurs and teaching words to early childhood.

Early childhood is growing and developing, following the laws of development, meaning that in general humans develop from fetuses, babies, children, adolescents, adults and the elderly; which speed of development varies, starting from fast, steady and slowing down, and stopping. The higher the age, the more experience is gained so that the more abilities the child gets. Growth and development have increased rapidly at an early age, from 0 to 5 years. This period is often referred to as the "Golden Age" phase³.

Child development is one aspect of human personality that does not stand alone because it is related to other aspects of personality and must be trained in children as early as possible so as not to hamper the tasks of further child development. The task of developing children at an early age is to achieve independence. Complete independence will be achieved by the end of adolescence, but independence will never be achieved or will only be achieved partially if development in early childhood does not provide a sound basis. Children who are not trained independently from an early age will become dependent individuals until adolescence and even adulthood. The most obvious example is elementary school age children who still need to be fed, bathed or a lot of help in activities that should have been done by themselves. Ability a person acquires gradually, that is, little by little. The bigger a person, the more his hearing, sight, and intellectual abilities increase until he reaches maturity and adulthood. Armed with hearing, sight, and conscience, the next child's development will be influenced as well as various educations from the surrounding environment⁴.

Independence in early childhood is very important, child independence supports children in learning to understand behavior choices and risks that must be held accountable by children. Therefore children must be given stimulation of play therapy, in this case parents must understand the child's condition, the level of growth and development of early childhood and how the child learns. Learning to stimulate play therapy is a journey that helps children feel independent, this is proven by the child being able to control over the child's body and helping him take more steps to become an independent individual⁵.

Early childhood development, both physically, emotionally, intellectually, and psychosocial, has problems that result in obstruction of children from reaching a level of development appropriate to their age. The emergence of various developmental barriers in early childhood is a phenomenon that needs to be further addressed so that sufferers can continue to live a good life and optimize the slightest ability they have. This is important because despite the various limitations, every human being has the same right to grow, develop, be accepted and carry out certain roles in society⁶.

To achieve maximum results, every educational process always requires collaboration between the school and parents. In principle, education should start from home⁷ and education will fail without parental participation⁸. One of the main requirements that parents must fulfill in striving for good cooperation with the school so that the education process runs optimally is to pay full attention to the child's growth as an individual, and not just attention to what the child achieves. Likewise with early childhood education, between parents and other family members and educational institutions must be able to work well together.

Emphasized that the mastery of various abilities in children will achieve better progress if in the process there is collaboration between parents and professional educational practitioners⁹. The knowledge and skills that children acquire at school will be more resilient and better controlled if they can also train them at home or outside the school environment with the help and direction of their parents. Looking at this explanation, it can be understood that parental participation in early childhood education programs is an important thing that must always be pursued. It's just that until now there is still no data showing that all parents of early childhood in Indonesia have understood this and are trying to fulfill it. It may even be that not all parents of early childhood are aware of the importance of their involvement in early childhood education in PAUD (Early Childhood Education) with day care¹⁰.

Parents act as educators while at home in early childhood. The family environment is also said to be the most important environment, because most of the lives of children are in the family, so that the most education received by early childhood is in the family. Parents must understand their nature and role as parents in raising children, equip themselves with knowledge of proper parenting, knowledge of the education that children undergo and knowledge of stimulation of play therapy, nutrition, growth and development of children, so there is no mistake in applying them. a form of educational pattern, especially in the formation of children's personalities in accordance with the goals of education, namely the intellectual life of the nation. Parenting education for parents who have early childhood in PAUD (Early Childhood Education) with day care is manifested in a way of assisting parents in stimulating play therapy and how to educate children⁵.

The importance of implementing the Early Childhood Care Nutrition and education program based on HI ECD on Day Care by using the series of modules "My Child is Healthy and Smart". 2) Parenting patterns, (3) Early childhood development principles, (4) Playing with children, (5) Fulfilling optimal children's nutrition, (6) Personal hygiene and food safety, (7) Integrated management of sick toddlers, (8) Protection, security and child safety and (9) Guidelines for implementing and monitoring HI ECD based programs¹¹.

Based on a preliminary study conducted in November 2019, it was found that from 70 PAUD with day care as many as 3500 pairs of parents and early childhood in the East Jakarta area, it was found that 85% of parents said that the child's weight and child development were impaired. Parents said they did not know more about the importance of stimulation with games to optimize children's growth and development. Based on the description above, it is necessary to conduct research on "Model Parenting Education and stimulation of play therapy in Early Childhood Growth and Development." As for the research sites in 11 PAUD schools with day care in Jakarta (Angrek, As Syifa, Kuncup Mekar, Cahaya Bunda, Ceria Indah, Dahlia, Darussalam, Harum, Kusuma, Sun, Roses)

This paper aims to describe the development and validation process of parenting education and stimulation of play therapy models for early education in day care facilities in Yogyakarta. To objective to develop and validate the module models of parenting education and stimulation of play therapy in early childhood growth and development.

I. METHODS

This research is the part of Research and Development (R&D) and aim to develop a product parenting education models. Research and Development is a research method used to produce certain products and test the effectiveness of these products¹². Research and Development has provided major innovations in the world of education. In this case, the researcher will develop a product in the form of "Parenting Education Model (Stimulation of Play Therapy for Early Childhood Growth and Development)", which will be used by PAUD teachers with day care and parents so that it can be applied in stimulating play therapy while in school. And at home. This research step modifies the development model of Borg and Gall in¹², namely (1) Research and information collection (conducting preliminary research and collecting preliminary information included in this step, including literature studies relating to the problems being studied and preparation to formulate research framework), (2) Planning (planning included in this step is formulating skills and expertise related to problems, determining objectives to be achieved at each stage), (3) Developing preliminary form of product (developing the initial form of the product, namely developing initial form of the product to be produced¹².

Included in this step are the preparation of supporting components, preparing guidelines and manuals and evaluating the appropriateness of supporting tools), (4) Preliminary field testing (initial field trials, namely conducting initial field trials on a limited scale involving as many as 22 subjects. In this step, data collection and analysis can be done by means of interviews, observations or questionnaires). Preliminary research is quantified by content validity ratio (CVR). (5) Main product revision (revision of trial results, namely making improvements to the initial product produced based on the initial trial results. This improvement is very likely to be done more than once, according to the results shown in limited trials, in order to obtain a product draft (model) (6) Main field testing (the main field trial involving enumerators), (7) Operational product revision (making improvements / enhancements to the wider trial results, so that the product being developed is already an operational model design which are ready to be validated), (8) Operational field testing (field implementation testing, namely the validation test step of the operational model that has been produced), (9) Final product revision (final product revision, namely making final improvements to the developed model to produce the final product / final), (10) Dissemination and implementation, namely steps to disseminate the product / model being developed gkan). In this research, steps 1 to 10 will be carried out.

In stage (1) research and information collection (conducting preliminary studies or preliminary research and collecting preliminary information), the researcher makes observations to obtain preliminary information which will be used as a basis and consideration in developing the book product "Model Parenting Education and Early Childhood Development)". Researchers collected information through interviews with 11 parents who had early childhood in 11 PAUD schools with day care, asking about the growth and development of early childhood during early childhood education with day care and interviews with several PAUD teachers with as many day care as 11 teachers in 11 PAUD schools.

In stage (2) planning (planning), what the researcher did was the design of the book development "Model Parenting Education (Stimulation of Playing Therapy for Early Childhood Growth and Development)".

In stage (3) develop a preliminary form of product (develop the initial form of the product), develop the initial form of the book product "Model Parenting Education (Stimulation of Play Therapy for Early Childhood Growth and Development)". At this stage, things that will be done are: (a) Compilation of components, (b) Design, (c) Product finishing, (d) Expert validation. In this expert

validation stage, the initial form of the product will be validated to be given an assessment of the product contents of the book "Model Parenting Education (Stimulation of Playing Therapy for Early Childhood Growth and Development)". Expert validation aims to test the feasibility of the product before testing the user, namely parents of early childhood and PAUD school teachers with day care. Stage (4) preliminary field testing (initial field trials). In the initial field trial phase, researchers conducted a limited trial of the initial form of the book product "Model Parenting Education (Stimulation of Playing Therapy for Early Childhood Growth and Development)". Stage (5) main product revision (revision of trial results). At the revision stage of the trial results, researchers made improvements based on the results of initial field trials, then the book "Model Parenting Education (Stimulation of Playing Therapy for Early Childhood Growth and Development)", which will then be applied to 110 pairs of parents and early childhood at 11 PAUD school with day care in Jakarta. (Orchids, As Syifa, Blossom Buds, Mother's Light, Ceria Indah, Dahlia, Darussalam, Harum, Kusuma, Matahari, Mawar).

Stage (6) main field testing (field testing involving enumerators). Field trials were applied to 110 pairs of parents and early childhood in 11 PAUD schools with day care in Jakarta (Anggrek, As Syifa, Kuncup Mekar, Cahaya Bunda, Ceria Indah, Dahlia, Darussalam, Harum, Kusuma, Matahari, Mawar). In the sixth stage, field trials could not be carried out due to the conditions of the Covid 19 pandemic outbreak, where the research areas were in 11 PAUD schools with day care in Jakarta (Anggrek, As Syifa, Kuncup Mekar, Cahaya Bunda, Ceria Indah, Dahlia, Darussalam, Harum, Kusuma, Matahari, Mawar). Experiencing LOCKDOWN and the existence of Large-Scale Social Restrictions (PSBB) in accordance with the Decree of the Governor of DKI Jakarta No / 959 of 2020. So that the field trial was to test the book "MODEL PARENTING EDUCATION (Stimulation of Play Therapy for Early Childhood Growth and Development)" in 11 PAUD schools in Yogyakarta (Ar Rahman, Cahaya Pelangi, Anggrek, Mutiara Hati, Among Putro, Niten, Lare Angon, Al Ishlah, Al Muttaqin, Melati and Nurul Islam).

Stage (7) operational product revision (making improvements or enhancements to the wider trial results, so that the product being developed is already an operational model design that is ready to be validated). Stage (8) Operational field testing (field implementation test, namely the validation test step of the operational model that has been produced), field testing is carried out on 110 pairs of parents and early childhood in 11 PAUD schools with day care in Jakarta (Anggrek, As Syifa, Kuncup Mekar, Cahaya Bunda, Ceria Indah, Dahlia, Darussalam, Harum, Kusuma, Matahari, Mawar)

. In the eighth stage the researcher used a quasi-experimental research design, namely research that aims to explain the effect and test the influence between variables through hypothesis testing. The form of research design time series design is a time series design that takes repeated measurements, before and after the experiment or treatment. This research is a quasi-experimental study with a pre-test-post-test design with control group design.

This stage cannot be carried out because there is a Covid 19 pandemic outbreak in East Jakarta, so further research cannot be carried out. So this research is only up to the book testing stage.

In the eighth stage, this research could not be carried out due to the conditions of the Covid 19 pandemic outbreak, where the research areas were in 11 PAUD schools with day care in Jakarta (Anggrek, As Syifa, Kuncup Mekar, Cahaya Bunda, Ceria Indah, Dahlia, Darussalam, Harum, Kusuma, Matahari, Mawar). Experiencing LOCKDOWN and the existence of Large-Scale Social Restrictions (PSBB) in accordance with the Decree of the Governor of DKI Jakarta No / 959 of 2020.

Stage (9) final product revision (final product revision, namely making final improvements to the developed model to produce the final / final product. Stage (10) dissemination and implementation, namely the step of disseminating the book "Model Parenting Education (Stimulation

of Playing Therapy for Growth and Early Childhood Development) ”, which was developed by researchers.

Place: 11 PAUD schools with day care in Jakarta (Anggrek, As Syifa, Kuncup Mekar, Cahaya Bunda, Ceria Indah, Dahlia, Darussalam, Harum, Kusuma, Matahari, Mawar)

Time: The study was conducted from March to November 2020 (duration of intervention was 9 months)

Book trial sites in 11 PAUD schools in Yogyakarta (Ar Rahman, Cahaya Pelangi, Anggrek, Mutiara Hati, Among Putro, Niten, Lare Angon, Al Ishlah, Al Muttaqin, Melati and Nurul Islam).

The research subjects or population were all pairs of parents with early childhood in 11 PAUD schools with day care in Jakarta (Anggrek, As Syifa, Kuncup Mekar, Cahaya Bunda, Ceria Indah, Dahlia, Darussalam, Harum, Kusuma, Matahari, Mawar). 110 couples of parents with early childhood. Early Childhood Education (PAUD) is a level of education before basic education, which is a coaching effort aimed at children from birth to six years of age carried out by providing educational stimuli to assist physical and spiritual growth and development so that children have readiness to enter further education organized in formal, non-formal and informal channels. Day care is a child care institution that can replace the role of parents in caring for and caring for children, when parents are working or not at home. In day care, children can learn to be more independent and also socialize better with their surroundings. Supported by facilities and activities that support child development.

Sample descriptions for book trials in 11 PAUD schools in Yogyakarta (Ar Rahman, Cahaya Pelangi, Anggrek, Mutiara Hati, Among Putro, Niten, Lare Angon, Al Ishlah, Al Muttaqin, Melati and Nurul Islam). Each PAUD 2 teachers and 1 parent of PAUD children.

The sample in this study were some couples of parents with early childhood in early childhood schools with day care in Jakarta (Anggrek, As Syifa, Kuncup Mekar, Cahaya Bunda, Ceria Indah, Dahlia, Darussalam, Harum, Kusuma, Matahari, Mawar) who taken by purposive sampling technique.

Samples for book trials in 11 PAUD schools in Yogyakarta (Ar Rahman, Cahaya Pelangi, Anggrek, Mutiara Hati, Among Putro, Niten, Lare Angon, Al Ishlah, Al Muttaqin, Melati and Nurul Islam). Each PAUD 2 teachers and 1 parent of PAUD children.

Inclusion Criteria Parents with ten early childhood children in each PAUD in 11 PAUD schools with day care in Jakarta (Anggrek, As Syifa, Kuncup Mekar, Cahaya Bunda, Ceria Indah, Dahlia, Darussalam, Harum, Kusuma, Matahari, Mawar) both boys male or female.

Book trials were conducted on pairs of parents with one early childhood in each PAUD 11 PAUD schools in Yogyakarta (Ar Rahman, Cahaya Pelangi, Anggrek, Mutiara Hati, Among Putro, Niten, Lare Angon, Al Ishlah, Al Muttaqin, Melati and Nurul Islam).

In this study, respondents were two groups of parents with early childhood in 11 PAUD schools with day care in Jakarta (Anggrek, As Syifa, Kuncup Mekar, Cahaya Bunda, Ceria Indah, Dahlia, Darussalam, Harum, Kusuma, Matahari, Mawar) as many as 55 pairs of parents and early childhood in each experimental group and control group. But this research could not be carried out due to the conditions of the Covid 19 pandemic outbreak, where the research areas were in 11 PAUD schools with day care in Jakarta (Anggrek, As Syifa, Kuncup Mekar, Cahaya Bunda, Ceria Indah, Dahlia, Darussalam, Harum, Kusuma, Matahari, Roses). Experiencing LOCKDOWN and the existence of Large-Scale Social Restrictions (PSBB) in accordance with the Decree of the Governor of DKI Jakarta No / 959 of 2020.

So that the field trial is by conducting a trial of the book "MODEL PARENTING EDUCATION (Stimulation of Play Therapy for Early Childhood Growth and Development)" in 11 PAUD schools in Yogyakarta (Ar Rahman, Cahaya Pelangi, Anggrek, Mutiara Hati, Among Putro, Niten, Lare Angon, Al Ishlah, Al Muttaqin, Melati and Nurul Islam).

Test Quantitative data analysis cannot be carried out so that the research steps that have been carried out by researchers are carried out by qualitative methods.

The study has been approve by Health Etic Commetee of Politeknik Kesehatan Kemenkes Yogyakarta at Description Of Ethical Appoval. With Number : e-KEPK/POLKESYO/0524/VI/2020.

II. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

In stage (1) research and information collection (conducting preliminary studies or preliminary research and collecting preliminary information), the researcher makes observations to obtain preliminary information which will be used as a basis and consideration in developing the book product "Model Parenting Education and Early Childhood Development)". Researchers collected information through interviews with 11 parents who had early childhood in 11 PAUD schools with day care, asking about the growth and development of early childhood during early childhood education with day care and interviews with several PAUD teachers with as many day care as 11 teachers in 11 PAUD schools.

In stage (2) planning (planning), what the researcher did was the design of the book development "Model Parenting Education (Stimulation of Playing Therapy for Early Childhood Growth and Development)". In the second stage (planning) the research team conducted a literature study and looked for journals related to the research material. Among other things about Parenting Education, Play Therapy Stimulation, Growth (Weight, Height, Head Circumference, Upper Arm Circumference, Chest Circumference, Abdominal Circumference), Development (Social Personal, fine motor skills, language, gross motor skills, cognitive, interests, emotions and morals), Growth and Development Monitoring, Factors that influence Growth and Development, Children's basic needs for growth and development, Stage of growth and physical development of children, Implementation of Play Therapy Stimulation for growth and development of early childhood and early childhood in PAUD (Education Early childhood).

In stage (3) develop a preliminary form of product (develop the initial form of the product), develop the initial form of the book product "Model Parenting Education (Stimulation of Play Therapy for Early Childhood Growth and Development)". At this stage, things that will be done are: (a) Compilation of components, (b) Design, (c) Product finishing, (d) Expert validation. In this expert validation stage, the initial form of the product will be validated to be given an assessment of the product contents of the book "Model Parenting Education (Stimulation of Playing Therapy for Early Childhood Growth and Development)". Expert validation aims to test the feasibility of the product before testing the user, namely parents of early childhood and PAUD school teachers with day care. In the third stage (develop the preliminary form of the product (develop the initial form of the product) compile the criteria for the preparation of the book, among others, from the aspects of the feasibility of the content (completeness of the material, depth of material, accuracy of concepts and definitions, accuracy of images and illustrations, accuracy of terms and current literature), The feasibility aspect of the presentation (consistency of the presentation system in learning activities, conceptual sequences) and the aspect of conceptual assessment (the relationship between the material being taught, constructivism, finding and reflection).

Stage (4) preliminary field testing (initial field trials). In the initial field trial phase, researchers conducted a limited trial of the initial form of the book product "Model Parenting Education (Stimulation of Playing Therapy for Early Childhood Growth and Development)".

Expert validation aims to test the feasibility of the product before testing the user, namely parents of PAUD children and PAUD teachers. Expert validation was carried out on two experts, namely child education experts, namely Prof. Djauhar Ismail, dr, Sp.A (K). Ph.D and Pror Dr. Ravik Karsidi, MS.

Input from the two experts is: 1) Content eligibility aspects. Material Completeness. It is recommended that the material on child growth and development be adapted to the literature from the Ministry of Health on Maternal and Child Health circulating in the community. Depth of Material. It does not need to be too deep because the target is a book for parents of PAUD children, so the material is easy to understand. Concept accuracy. Concepts and definitions are adapted to the book Maternal and Child Health (KIA), guidelines for stimulating detection and early intervention on child development and need dictionary or glossary terms. Image Accuracy. Drawings should be made by yourself and Indonesian models. Diagrams and illustrations should be made easy to understand and attractive. Accuracy of Terms. The title needs to be revised in terms of action therapy in children with developmental deviations carried out by people who have been educated. Library Updates. The library is quite complete and up to date in accordance with the guidelines. 2) Feasibility aspects of presentation. Systematic consistency. It is better if the description in the book uses the author's own sentence, it will make it easier for people to read and avoid plagiarism. Concept clutter

The conceptuality is quite in accordance with the concept. 3) Conceptual Assessment Aspects. The relationship between the material being taught. The purpose of this manual for parents should be clear, for example in the areas of knowledge, attitudes and practice of implementation or evaluation. Constructivism. The pictures in the book are made a model of Indonesian people so that parents are sure they can implement them. Find (Inquiry). It is worth emphasizing the novelty of this book and the guidelines from other books. Putting the model guide as a matter of findings by the author is very important to give meaning to the innovation of the book. Reflection. Parents of PAUD children are given the opportunity to ask questions and provide suggestions on how to evaluate implementation.

From the expert's judgment, the results were LDR (Eligible for Revision), there were several inputs that had to be revised. Then improvements have been made to the book. The reliability value of 0.69 means that the instrument / manual is reliable.

Stage (5) main product revision (revision of trial results). At the revision stage of the trial results, researchers made improvements based on the results of initial field trials, then the book "Model Parenting Education (Stimulation of Playing Therapy for Early Childhood Growth and Development)", which will then be applied to 110 pairs of parents and early childhood at 11 PAUD school with day care in Jakarta (Angrek, As Syifa, Kuncup Mekar, Cahaya Bunda, Ceria Indah, Dahlia, Darussalam, Harum, Kusuma, Matahari, Mawar).

In the fifth stage, field trials could not be carried out in East Jakarta due to the conditions of the Covid 19 pandemic, where the research areas were in 11 PAUD schools with day care in East Jakarta (Angrek, As Syifa, Kuncup Mekar, Cahaya Bunda, Ceria Indah, Dahlia, Darussalam, Harum, Kusuma, Matahari, Mawar). Experiencing LOCKDOWN and the existence of Large-Scale Social Restrictions (PSBB) in accordance with the Decree of the Governor of DKI Jakarta No / 959 of 2020. So that the field trial was to test the book "MODEL PARENTING EDUCATION (Stimulation of Play Therapy for Early Childhood Growth and Development)" in 11 PAUD schools in Yogyakarta (Ar Rahman, Cahaya Pelangi, Angrek, Mutiara Hati, Among Putro, Niten, Lare Angon, Al Ishlah, Al Muttaqin, Melati and Nurul Islam).

The trial of the book "Model Parenting Education (Stimulation of Playing Therapy for Early Childhood Growth and Development)" was conducted on 1 parent in each PAUD and 2 teachers in each PAUD (22 PAUD teachers and 11 parents). The results of the input book trial from 22 PAUD teachers included: the material was not too long and used terms that could be understood and applied by parents of PAUD children, illustrated images that were easy to observe and could be applied in early childhood education schools. The use of the term Parenting can use language that is easily understood by parents of PAUD children and the pictures in the book are adjusted to the growth and development of early childhood. The results of the trial of input books from parents of PAUD children include: language so that it is easy to understand does not use foreign languages and Latin terms and uses sentences that are easily understood by parents of PAUD children.

The initial field trial was limited to 22 PAUD teachers from 11 PAUD in Yogyakarta and 11 parents from 11 PAUD in Yogyakarta. With the results of the validity test with the results of r table for $n = 33$ is 0.514 or significancy <0.05 means that the results are valid. Reliability test with Alpha Cronbarch's > 0.6 is said to be reliable, meaning that it has sufficient reliability.

Stage (6) main field testing (field testing involving enumerators). Field trials were applied to 110 pairs of parents and early childhood in 11 PAUD schools with day care in Jakarta (Anggrek, As Syifa, Kuncup Mekar, Cahaya Bunda, Ceria Indah, Dahlia, Darussalam, Harum, Kusuma, Matahari, Mawar). In the sixth stage, field trials could not be carried out due to the conditions of the Covid 19 pandemic outbreak, where the research areas were in 11 PAUD schools with day care in Jakarta (Anggrek, As Syifa, Kuncup Mekar, Cahaya Bunda, Ceria Indah, Dahlia, Darussalam, Harum, Kusuma, Matahari, Mawar). Experiencing LOCKDOWN and the existence of Large-Scale Social Restrictions (PSBB) in accordance with the Decree of the Governor of DKI Jakarta No / 959 of 2020. So that the field trial was to test the book "MODEL PARENTING EDUCATION (Stimulation of Play Therapy for Early Childhood Growth and Development)" in 11 PAUD schools in Yogyakarta (Ar Rahman, Cahaya Pelangi, Anggrek, Mutiara Hati, Among Putro, Niten, Lare Angon, Al Ishlah, Al Muttaqin, Melati and Nurul Islam).

The results of the input for the book trial "Model Parenting Education (Stimulation of Playing Therapy for Early Childhood Growth and Development)" were from the input of 2 expert examiners and 22 PAUD teachers from 11 PAUD in Yogyakarta and 11 parents of PAUD children from 11 PAUD in Yogyakarta (Ar Rahman, Cahaya Pelangi, Anggrek, Mutiara Hati, Among Putro, Niten, Lare Angon, Al Ishlah, Al Muttaqin, Melati and Nurul Islam) have revised the book and it can be printed for further research materials or materials with the instrument of Child Growth and Development Early.

Stage (7) operational product revision (making improvements or enhancements to the wider trial results, so that the product being developed is already an operational model design that is ready to be validated).

The book "Model Parenting Education (Stimulation of Playing Therapy for Early Childhood Growth and Development)" after being tested is then revised and ready to print with the ISBN.

Stage (8) Operational field testing (field implementation test, namely the validation test step of the operational model that has been produced), field testing is carried out on 110 pairs of parents and early childhood in 11 PAUD schools with day care in Jakarta (Anggrek, As Syifa, Kuncup Mekar, Cahaya Bunda, Ceria Indah, Dahlia, Darussalam, Harum, Kusuma, Matahari, Mawar). In the eighth stage, this research could not be carried out due to the conditions of the Covid 19 pandemic outbreak, where the research areas were in 11 PAUD schools with day care in Jakarta (Anggrek, As Syifa, Kuncup Mekar, Cahaya Bunda, Ceria Indah, Dahlia, Darussalam, Harum, Kusuma, Sun, Mawar). Experiencing LOCKDOWN and the existence of Large-Scale Social Restrictions (PSBB) in

accordance with the Decree of the Governor of DKI Jakarta No / 959 of 2020. So that Parenting Education Intervention and Play Therapy Stimulation for 4 months which should be done starting with a pre test and ending with a post test cannot be done.

Stage (9) final product revision (final product revision, namely making final improvements to the developed model to produce the final / final product. Stage (10) dissemination and implementation, namely the step of disseminating the book "Model Parenting Education (Stimulation of Playing Therapy for Growth and Early Childhood Development)", which was developed by researchers.

Stages 9 and 10 cannot be implemented to print books that have been finalized after the expert testing process of 2 experts and the trial process of 22 PAUD teachers and 11 parents of PAUD children from 11 PAUD schools in Yogyakarta (Ar Rahman, Cahaya Pelangi, Anggrek, Mutiara Hati, Among Putro, Niten, Lare Angon, Al Ishlah, Al Muttaqin, Melati and Nurul Islam), so they cannot enter printing with ISBN.

Play therapy and social interaction in early childhood can improve early childhood social personal, including learning the basics of language through games and interacting with parents or caregivers in a meaningful way and looking at the faces of early childhood then starting to talk to early childhood⁵. . Stimulating early childhood to make eye contact by holding a child's favorite toy or object and waiting for the child to see before handing over the toy includes blowing a balloon or rolling a ball. Early childhood are trained to recognize vocabulary that is easily understood by early childhood by providing examples and holding toys, for example early childhood children are asked to hold the ball and say the ball¹³.

Early childhood are trained to imitate movements such as clapping hands, waving, shaking hands and knocking on doors. Stimulation can also take the form of inviting young children to sing, clap their hands, imitate movements or play games together. In some early childhood, the ability to mimic a sound or hum is better than communication. This can be used as a gateway to the world of early childhood. Although parents also have to be vigilant, don't because early age children enjoy humming continuously and then their communication skills are not developed. Simple games are also good for early childhood stimulation such as cheek-ba play. Moreover, this game requires the presence of other people. With this game parents can introduce early childhood to the people around them¹⁴.

This kind of game can and should be done by all family members. It can be done by different people, early childhood children are given the opportunity to feel the same stimulus in different settings (playing with mother in the room, with father on the terrace and so on) . Sensory integration activities that can be done for early childhood include making handicrafts, such as forming clay with various different forms or painting by holding early childhood's hands and teaching how to paint so that early childhood can paint on their own¹⁵.

Early childhood who have a healthy relationship with their family (full of care and affection for their parents) can facilitate early childhood language development. Conversely, if the relationship between early childhood and their parents is not healthy, then the language development of early childhood tends to experience disorders such as stuttering, unclear words, speaking harshly and impolitely and feeling afraid to express their opinions. The environment in which they live also affects the language development of early childhood, where the village environment is still close kinship and socialization with the environment is still good, so early childhood contact with children of the same age is still quite intensive. Early childhood contact with children of the same age encourages children's language development¹⁴.

Communication is a process where early childhoods exchange information and convey thoughts and feelings, where there is a message sender who formulates a message and the recipient decodes the message / understands the message. Language as a means of communication, namely to make messages easier to convey and understand and the communication process occurs through language. Forms of language can be in the form of signs, gestures, writing, pictures and speech and forms of verbal communication are the main means of expressing thoughts and feelings. Verbal communication uses words that represent various aspects of individual reality followed by verbal actions or cues as a whole³.

For motor development and the growth of the body's muscles, directed stimulation is required by playing, exercising or exercising. Early childhood should be introduced to sports as early as possible, for example throwing / catching a ball, jumping, playing rope, riding a bicycle, etc.). Play therapy is a valuable "school" for children so that their intellectual development is optimal¹⁴.

Early childhood still need the help of parents and PAUD teachers in doing this. Development of brain function which includes social and affective fields, verbal (language) and non-verbal communication, imagination, flexibility, scope of interest (interest), cognition and attention. So it takes a process of time to form fine motor development in the absence of effective therapy⁵.

The use of image media can help encourage early childhood to generate interest in learning. Assist in their cognitive abilities, language and help them interpret and memorize the content of the material from a book or text. The use of picture cards as a learning medium is in accordance with the conditions of early childhood cognitive development, because early childhood gets understanding through symbolic activities. The ability of picture card media in generating attention and interest in early childhood is in accordance with the function of the media, namely as a communication bridge that makes it easier for early childhood to obtain appropriate perceptions¹⁴.

Another method used is stimulation play therapy, in which emotional development is the focus. The stimulation of play therapy is usually done by playing roles between adults and early childhood, and trying to develop social skills and social interactions. The ability and development of early childhood needs to be stimulated by parents so that early childhood can grow and develop optimally and according to their age. Play therapy stimulation is the stimulation (vision, speech, hearing, touch) that comes from the environment of early childhood. Early childhood children who receive targeted stimulation of play therapy will develop faster than early childhood who do not even get stimulated play therapy⁵.

Play therapy stimulation can also serve as a beneficial enhancer for early childhood development. Various kinds of stimulation of play therapy such as visual stimulation (vision), verbal (talk), auditive (hearing), tactile (touch), can optimize early childhood development. Giving stimulation of play therapy will be more effective if it takes into account the needs of early childhood in accordance with the stages of age development. The stimulation of visual and verbal play therapy at the onset of early childhood development is an important initial stimulation, because it can cause expressive properties such as raising eyebrows, opening mouth and eyes such as expressions of astonishment, etc. In addition, early childhood also requires tactile stimulation, the lack of tactile stimulation can cause social, emotional and motor behavior deviations in early childhood⁵.

Attention and affection are also the stimulation that early childhood needs, for example by talking, caressing, kissing, playing etc. The stimulation of play therapy will create a sense of security and self-confidence in early childhood, so that early childhood will be more responsive to their environment and more developed. In early childhood who are able to walk and talk, they will be happy to explore and manipulate their environment. This motive can be strengthened or weakened by the environment through a number of reactions given to the child's behavior. For example, early

childhood will learn to know which behavior makes the mother happy / gets praise from the mother, and which behavior gets angry from the mother. Early childhood raised in a responsive environment will show high exploratory behavior. Verbal stimulation is also needed at this early childhood development stage¹⁴.

The importance of parenting education for parents of early childhood who play a very important role as a companion for early childhood, because early childhood cannot be left alone without a companion. So if early childhood is outside the classroom during recess or doing activities outside the classroom, the PAUD teacher at school acts as a companion for early childhood⁵.

What PAUD teachers do at the time of mentoring, in addition to maintaining and supervising early childhood behavior, is engaging in active interaction with early childhood in order to increase understanding in various fields, namely by providing information and experiences, by telling early childhood what they hold. and observing and explaining various events experienced, introducing rules that need to be obeyed, for example about school entry hours, rest hours, what can and cannot be done by early childhood and habituation of how to behave politely to others. Parents must always follow where early childhood is located, tell what is held and seen by early childhood and explain various events experienced by children, parents need to give meaning to children's lives¹.

Through socialization, early childhood will get more social stimulation which is beneficial for the social development of early childhood. At this time in Indonesia, a program for early childhood has been developed which aims to stimulate early childhood development as early as possible, using APE (educational game tool)⁵. Educational Game Tool (APE) is a game tool that can optimize early childhood development according to their age and level of development, and is useful for the development of physical aspects (activities that support or stimulate children's physical growth), language aspects (by practicing speaking, using correct sentences), aspects of intelligence (with recognition of voice, size, shape, color etc.), and social aspects (especially in relation to interactions between mothers and early childhood, family and society). Play therapy, talking to young children, and affection are "foods" that are important for early childhood development, as are the need for food for body growth¹².

Playing for early childhood is not just filling free time, but through stimulation of play therapy, early childhood will learn to control and coordinate their muscles, involving their feelings, emotions and thoughts. So that with play therapy, early childhood gets various life experiences, besides that, if it is confessed with the parents, the relationship between parents and early childhood becomes more intimate and parents will also immediately find out if there is a disruption in early child development⁵.

III. CONCLUSION

The initial form of parenting education model book products and play therapy stimulation models in early childhood in PAUD (Early Childhood Education) has been formed "Model Parenting Education (Stimulation of Play Therapy for Early Childhood Growth and Development)". Initial field trials with material expert validation / expert testing of parenting education model books and play therapy stimulation models in early childhood in PAUD (Early Childhood Education) have been carried out on 2 expert examiners with LDR results (Suitable for Revision) there are several entries that need to be revised. Then improvements have been made to the book. The reliability value of 0.69 means that the instrument / manual is reliable. Field trials and revisions of the results of field trials of parenting education model books and play therapy stimulation models in early childhood in PAUD (Early Childhood Education) have been carried out with 22 PAUD teachers and 11 parents of PAUD children results r table for n = 33 is 0.514 or the significancy <0.05 means the result is valid.

Reliability test with Alpha Cronbach's $\alpha > 0.6$ is said to be reliable, meaning that it has sufficient reliability.

Acknowledgment

For early childhood in PAUD with day care. Parenting education models and stimulation of play therapy can improve early childhood growth and development in early childhood with day care. For families who have early childhood in PAUD day care. The parenting education model can be used as a family guide to stimulate play therapy to increase early childhood growth and development in early childhood education with day care. For PAUD teachers with day care. The parenting education model can be used as a guide for teachers to carry out parenting education and provide stimulation of play therapy in order to increase the growth and development of early childhood in early childhood with day care.

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